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‘Coming Back’ And Partition: Mobility and Memory Creating Liquid Borders in Amitav Ghosh’s *The Shadow Lines* and Geetanjali Shree’s *Tomb of Sand*

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Abstract:

The idea of borders has been historically designed for the sake of maintaining a power politics of spaces, properties, bodies, and even life and death. Borders, both physically and metaphorically, embody a sense of control, obedience, restriction, and order; and therefore, are perceived in terms of impenetrability and solidity. Such a perception further triggers militarized violence, technological abuse, and criminalization of anything that could potentially be a threat to the established narrative of border politics. However, Partition narratives and anecdotes reveal the gaps in the meta-narrative of borders by unmasking the ‘liquid’ nature of it. This unmasking is triggered by memory and mobility that motivates both a physical and a mental movement across the borders, further demystifying the rhetoric of ‘other’ through mental maps, cultural hybridisation, and memo-narratives. This paper studies how memory and mobility endanger the meta-narrative of border and associated border politics in Amitav Ghosh’s *The Shadow Lines* and Geetanjali Shree’s *Tomb of Sand*, by channelising agency through subversive gendered bodies.

Keywords: Border Politics, Liquid Borders, Memory, Mobility, Meta-narrative.

Introduction

The notion of borders has been historically intertwined with the act of demarcating cultural and political domains in association with sovereignty and power over property. The power politics embedded within the notion of borders, therefore, include a sense of control, limitation, legality, order, exclusion, restriction and rhetoric of the 'other'. Despite being such a rigid and hegemonic body of power, it has, in the course of history, encouraged transgression, contestation, and disobedience. Critics like Mabel Mora further saw the interconnection between national borders with factors like capitalism and migratory laws, and perceived this to be nothing less than a 'Kafkaesque reality'. Furthermore, the biopolitics of borders also include notions of militarized violence, technology, naturalized inequality, authoritarian mechanisms, and criminalization of civil disobedience, dehumanization, and compulsive displacement under the guise of ecological and political balance. Therefore, when one looks back at moments in history that have triggered an overwhelming assertion of the biopolitics of borders, such as the Partition of India in and after 1947, it is to be perceived not only as a legacy bearer of the ghetto mentality, but based on its contribution, is the construction of a meta-narrative. This meta-narrative, in case of India, is more layered because even though the nature of the aftermath of the partition(s) in the west and the east cannot be generalized, the border politics associated with the Partition had in it rooted a religious and communal discourse that manifested in complex forms like caste and class hierarchies. Thus, border politics and border, as an embodiment of power, are often conceptualized in terms of impenetrability, opacity, and solidity. This almost creates an illusion that, for instance, smoke from a chimney near the border of India can never mix with the air of Pakistan or Bangladesh; or perhaps the river in India that eventually geographically flows into Bangladesh will not carry the residue dumped into it. However, it is mobility (both physical and mental) as a result of migration and

memory that threatens the meta-narrative of the border. On a metaphorical level, it is more of a liquefaction of border, as Mabel Moraña writes that the very idea of ‘liquid borders’ evokes an image of “pervasive encounters between the massive fluxes of transnational migrants and the material and intangible obstacles imposed as proliferating dispositifs of border governmentality in the globalized world.”

In Amitav Ghosh’s *The Shadow Lines*, this very notion of the solid, impenetrable border is questioned when the grandmother who once migrated to India, before the actual partition, after years, plans on ‘going/coming’ back to Bangladesh – her birthplace, she curiously enquires of her grandson whether she would be able to see the border between India and East Pakistan (Bangladesh) from the plane and further insists that there must be something that marks the border like trenches, or soldiers, or at least a barren strip of land. Even though she is told that in the modern world the borders are within the airports and it is not like a ‘map’, her statement that follows not only threatens the meta-narrative of border but also questions the rationality that preceded the making of borders – “...if there’s no difference, both sides will be the same, it’ll be just like it used to be before, when we used to catch a train in Dhaka and get off in Calcutta the next day without anybody stopping us. What was it all for then – Partition and all the killing and everything- if there isn’t something in between?” (Ghosh 110). Other than the physicality of borders, Ghosh’s novel also addresses the penetrability of borders, as by the end of its narrative, in the climactic edge, the novel eventually reveals how the narrator’s relative Tridib died in Dhaka, Bangladesh, in a violent unrest due to the ripples of the communal riot that happened in Kashmir, India. Similar to the notion of impenetrability, the myth-making associated with borders also includes a media-propagated essentialized rhetoric of the ‘Other’. While borders become interchangeable with the ‘other side’ in communal discourses, as a matter of fact, what happens is dualistic in nature - a re-definition of the side one inhabits and a mythic imagination of the ‘other’

side, all in relation to the border. This is exemplified in a rather interesting micro-cosmic anecdote within Ghosh's *The Shadow Lines*, where Th'amma, aka the grandmother narrates a story from her childhood. Here, the house they used to live in '1/31 Jindabaha Lane' (99) in Dhaka, was divided into two halves owing to strained familial relationships. Therefore, Th'amma and her sister, being no more able to go beyond their demarcated space to the other side of the house, called it the 'upside down' and made up narratives like tea is drunk in buckets and not from cups or, that people on that side bathe in the kitchen. This is a symbolic and micro-reflection of 'othering' that happened in the form of casteist jokes and stereotypes, as in the case of Bengal, like *ghoti-bangal* or *Bhadralok* and *Chotolok*. However, such a practice of 'othering' is not just an individualist or regional stance, instead is further backed by the state to ensure its propagandist narratives. *The Shadow Lines* describes how the formation of a nation is not a linear process but rather one that entails, on one hand, "a broader homogenization despite seeming differences, of what lies within the boundaries and a projection of alien-ness upon what is situated outside" (Mukherjee). Therefore, further linked to this dominant discourse regarding the 'other side' is the notion of the nation, where individuals are motivated to define their identities on these lines of essentialized binaries and materialised differences. Forming an identity on these grounds becomes more relevant when the question of the ambiguities associated with crossing the borders crops up.

Now, considering the threatened notion of impenetrability leading to 'liquid borders', borders themselves become a porous and liminal space, and it is this liminality that makes the act of 'crossing' the borders an act of transgression. A sense of transgression is inherent within the very construct of borders, which gets heightened in Geetanjali Shree's *Tomb of Sand*, where by the end of the novel the narrator's mother emerges as the model for the self that, like a *deshdrohi* _traitor of the nation_ situates her selfhood in the essential 'other'. Homi K. Bhabha further writes that the sense of liminality, or the

borders as the ‘third’ space, is asserted as borders emerges as a sensitive space that strip one of its meaning or seduces a misreading of it amidst the contestation “of everyday life, between classes, genders, races, nations...the reality of the limit...of culture is rarely theorized outside well-intentioned moralist polemics against prejudice...” (Bhabha 34) and eventually cultures are embedded within an inherent politics of otherness which is closely related to the meaning making and symbol forming activities leading to de-centered structures. Thus, while borders themselves are characterized by liminality, the cultures associated with borders are inclusive of a hegemonic structure and therefore, on one hand, are centralized, while on the other hand, are decentralized due to hybridity caused by migration and cross-border mobility.

Mental Maps and re-imagining homelands

Narratives, or more precisely, anecdotes based on memory and nostalgia, abound in the literary canon of Partition texts. These memories construct, reconstruct, and even destroy in the process of re-drawing the borders and countering cartographic absolutism. Maurice Halbwachs observes how everything is immersed in a cultural whole, and memory too becomes a cultural artefact. Even though it is a fluid and unstable construct, memory, as Halbwachs rightly points out, is intimately related to place, a particular locale. In remembering the events of 1947, survivors invariably reconstruct the past on the basis of their experience of a particular place, a neighbourhood, a village, a camp and so on. The spatialization of memory “perfectly reconciles the division in history through particularizing the homogeneous, unified march of historical events through anchoring them in particular locales. This spatial dimension of memory enables it to reconstruct places or sites erased or marginalized in official histories” (Roy 32-33). This function of memory is nowhere as evident as in memories of remembered villages and cities marked by composite, cosmopolitan cultural formations that have been subsequently overwritten by sectarian nationalisms. The remembered Lahore of old

Lahorites or Lucknow of old Lucknowites reinscribed by their appropriation in religious nationalism survives solely in the collective memories of their older residents. The mapping of the events of 1947 on the forgotten cartographies and landmarks of pre-Partitioned cities, towns, and villages provides a glimpse into the socio-cultural history of these spaces that are either overlooked or erased in historians' histories.

The borders of the mind in Partition narratives do not coincide with the acknowledged 'true maps', and therefore, the maps of the mind or the mental maps disrupt the contours of real places. Edward Said, in his theorising of the dynamics between space, place, memory and home, explains how desire and the unconscious mind function in producing imaginary geographies of both 'home' and the 'other'. According to Said, imagining homelands, or fictional geographies based on past experiences and memories, be it cities, villages, towns, or neighborhood, follows the logic of memory in the selection of the convivial, and the erasure of the traumatic experience. Nostalgic homelands map an emotional geography of spaces and places whose spatial coordinates are produced through the relations between human beings and their environment, and social, economic and cultural activities and relations between groups. This emotional intensity in imagination is closely related to the idea of desired homeland or the birth place that weaves a mesh of speech, food, culture, language, customs, rituals, architectural objects and spaces, institutions and so on. The emotional affiliation and affective belonging to the homeland imbues it with a sense of enchantment that produces affective magical cities of memory. The Bombay of Sa'adat Hasan Manto and Salman Rushdie, the Lahore of Manju Kapoor and Bapsi Sidhwa, the Lucknow of Joginder Paul and the Lyallpur of Gurcharan Das construct a fictional city, an "imaginary homeland" lost in the past that is a "different country" produced through the desire of the city (Rushdie 1982). These fictional representations of the city are replicated in the

testimonial accounts and memoirs of Partition survivors whose nostalgic recollections construct them as the comforting space of home.

If memory becomes primal to the reconstruction of the lost 'home', memory narratives around partition do not just contain the cartography of the lost home but also, as mentioned earlier, the horrors and trauma associated with it, leading to the unveiling of something that ought to be hidden. Geetanjali Shree's novel *Tomb of Sand* introduces Ma as a depressed 80-year-old, and a woman so small she could 'slip' through anywhere. Throughout the initial part of the novel, only her back is visible to the reader. She is found lying, facing the wall, in a civil servant's bungalow in north India. However later she leaves the house and crosses the border with her daughter into Pakistan and travels to Lahore, where she lived as a girl, and then to Khyber-Pakhtunkhwa, where she goes looking for her ex-husband, Anwar, and claims an identity for herself that does not only transgress the nation-state borders but also her relation to any other hegemonic embodiment like the family. Thus, the revealing of an ex-husband is almost the Freudian '*unheimlich*' that memory triggers. This is further related to the notion of xenophobia which, according to Julia Kristeva, is a form of abjection which constitutes the one labeled as a foreigner to be a border abject. However, border abject, like Ma, has the power to disorient the order that controls one's identity and socio-cultural mechanisms.

In the initial chapter of Geetanjali Shree's novel, Ma always turns her back and is later shown practicing falling so as to confront death at the Khyber Pass which stands as a manifestation of the border of India and Pakistan. She navigates through the lanes and the neighborhood of Pakistan that she used to be familiar with in her childhood and literally could reach a crossroad and envision what shops and houses might follow upon taking a particular turn. Her relentless geographic sketching of the Pakistan in her memory in the bordered Pakistan brings into realization the lacunae in the very notion of border. Her Pakistan (though there is nothing called Pakistan in her days) can be situated in

the tradition of mental maps that reconstructs spaces that have disappeared, like Ma's borderless Pakistan, and traces alternative cartographies, exposing the biases of objectified cartographic knowledge such as socio-spatial hierarchies that construct the world map. Like Ma's mental map, there is also many others, like Chela Ram's mental map of the microspace of the shops and homes in the Main Bazaar in Bhakkar owned by his immediate and extended family, in which the iconic Jinnah Gate and the Gurdwara form the points of orientation; drawn by his grandson, it is a telling sketch of the domination of the Hindu trader in the Muslim-dominated Bhakkar city (in Kalra) (Roy 143). All the seven shops, including grocery, textiles, and luggage, drawn based on the mental map, with the exception for a Muslim teli (oil mill press), belong to Hindus, predominantly from single families, thus mapping the Hindus' domination of the city's trade as well as the trading community's location on the map of the city. Chela Ram's memory map elicits an economic geography of the city and nostalgia for the space of trade constructed through kinship networks. Similar is the map of Jatinder Sethi, hailing from an educated family of lawyers who had migrated from Jhang to Lyallpur, offers a charted map of the architectural plan of the Lyallpur city and its famous eight bazaars, which was a replica of the Union Jack, as a tribute to the Queen of England- "A rectangle containing a Cross and two Diagonals. All the eight bazaars started from the Ghanta Ghar (clock tower), which was the focal point of the town. Four of the eight bazaars were perpendicular, and you could see the full face of the Ghanta Ghar. The other four bazaars were diagonal to the Ghanta Ghar; from these bazaars, you could only see the diagonal face of the tower." (Roy 145).

Later in Shree's novel, Ma says that one must not accept the border and continues:

It's [the border] something that surrounds an existence, it is a person's perimeter. No matter how large, no matter how small. The edge of a handkerchief, the border of a tablecloth, the embroidery around my shawl. The edges of the sky. The beds of flowers

in this yard. The borders of fields. The parapet around this roof. A picture frame.

Everything has a border. (Shree)

Likewise, Amitav Ghosh's novel leads to its narrator, in his pursuit of discovering how a communal riot in Kashmir, India led to the death of his relative in Bangladesh, ends up with a mental map that triggers the epiphany that the solid lines that divides countries turn into glass through which it is clearly visible that Chiang Mai in Thailand is spatially closer to Calcutta than New Delhi, and Chengdu in China is nearer than Srinagar is. With the blurring of borders, or maps turning into mirrors, the narrator writes – "I, in Calcutta had only to look into the mirror to be in Dhaka; a moment when each city was the reverted image of the other, locked into an irreversible symmetry by the line that was to set us free – our looking-glass border" (Ghosh 170). Thus both Ghosh's and Shree's novels dismantle the notions of impenetrability, un-negotiability and cartographic absolutism associated with border to the point that it makes the very 'border' susceptible to collapse.

Memory and redefining border cultures and narratives

Controlled mobility, restrictions, limitations, and obedience are embedded within the very framework of the Partition and border politics. Partition narratives often consist of nostalgic anecdotes, based on memory, like that of Wafa. In a border village, Baltibazar, Kargil, Wafa's memory (2017) fills in the missing gaps in the authoritative account of the permanent closure of the border on the west through recounting the tragic fate of his divided family:

Till 1965, despite Partition, people used to cross the border illegally. No restrictions were imposed. Total restrictions were imposed between India and Pakistan after the war of 1965. After that, the movement of people across the border was severely restricted.

(Roy 36)

His personal narrative of his family that hailed from Paarik (which formed a part of Kharmang now in Pakistan Occupied Kashmir) but had migrated to Baltibazar for work provides an unexpected glimpse into the macronarrative of the closure of an ancient trade route between India and Central Asia, namely the Kargil-Skardoo route:

We used to go to Pakistan and they used to visit us. Goods were freely exchanged between us. You must have heard about the Kargil-Skardoo route. This was one of the routes to Central Asia, from here to Srinagar, Skardoo, Zanskar, Leh. Business (barter system) was most common during those days along this route. There was not much development in the region like today and we had to travel from one place to another for work. Those were the days of scarcity. No democratic government existed like today. We were under the rule of kings (the Dogra Rulers); kings were oppressive, due to which, some people fled from the region. (Roy 36)

In these narratives, dictated by memory of a place in relation to the ambiguity that results out of the subject position of the mobile body that is neither the 'other' nor the propagator of the rhetoric of 'other', these individuals 'contaminate' the idea of centralized cultures because their memory and geographical space lead to what Homi K. Bhabha terms 'partial cultures' (qtd. in Bond and Rapson 8). Their mobility across borders lead to cultural hybridization and Bhabha adds, "Hybrid agencies find their voice in a dialectic that does not seek cultural supremacy or sovereignty. They deploy the partial culture from which they emerge to construct visions of community, and versions of historic memory, that give narrative form to the minority positions they occupy; the outside of the inside: the part in the whole (8)." To further this, the ground for hybridization led to the emergence of the notion of transculturality. The transculturality in *Tomb of Sand* manifest via memory which leads to

two simultaneous ends. One, it shows the trajectory of how memory travels within and between nationally defined cultures that allows mobility, and Ma travels the land in her memory. Second, the transcultural memory lets one move ‘beyond’ the borders and the notion of borders as containers of the knowledge of the past. This is argued by Andreas Huyssen as he claims. “The form in which we think of the past is increasingly memory without borders rather than national history within borders. Modernity has brought with it a very real compression of time and space. Nevertheless, in the register of imaginaries, it has also expanded our horizons of time and space beyond the local, the national and even the international” (Huyssen 2003) (qtd. in Bond and Rapson 16). Thus, if the novel is read as a travelogue, it is more a transcultural travel on the topography of memory which can break through the isomorphic imagination of border.

Most available and accessible partition narratives are mostly male experiences, which makes the experience of borders not just hegemonic but also patriarchal. Both Amitav Ghosh’s *The Shadow Lines* and Geetanjali Shree’s *Tomb of Sand* resist the patriarchally conceived notions of border by projecting the geographic landscape as well as the memoryscape under the feminine gaze of the three women characters that actually travel across the borders. In the case of Ghosh’s *The Shadow Lines*, it becomes comparatively difficult to trace the nuances of feminine gaze on the hegemonic narrative of the border because of the pre-dominance of the male narrator. However, the feminine gaze does interestingly manifest in terms of, again, memory via the anecdotes of Thamma of her childhood at Dhaka, and also in her active role in actually exploring the ‘other’ side in metaphorical terms as she had to enter the ‘other’ side of their ancestral house in order to bring back her old uncle. In case of *Tomb of Sand*, the patriarchal voice is sidelined as the narrative invests mainly in the tradition of narratives that occurs in a micro level through memory and micro-histories. Moreover, in Shree’s novel, Ma insists on standing as an act of resistance and has prepared herself for death in the borders.

This situates the texts in the tradition of works on partition like Urvashi Butalia's *The Other Side of Silence* that intends to bring out the silenced narrative of partition by, for example, interviewing women in the intimate space of their houses. In these memo-narratives, the border-nation construction is a largely patriarchal and male-centric occurrence. Therefore, women's memory emerges as a counter memory to the objective, supposedly rational and official male-narrative of partition that made its place within the history textbooks. Thus memory, again, emerges as a potential means of giving voice to the subalterns, eventually exposing the partial, patriarchal and manipulated meta-narratives of border and state.

Conclusion

Contextualizing border politics of the Indian post-Independence Partition(s) via a close look at Amitav Ghosh's *The Shadow Lines* and Geetanjali Shree's *Tomb of Sand*, the meta-narrative of border itself gets threatened and deconstructed. Borders, which, are predominantly conceived in terms of solidity in order to maintain its political status as an embodiment of power that dictates life, body, and cultures, when studied by taking into consideration micro-narratives, subject positions, gender positions and memory, lead us to the notion of liquid borders. This 'liquid' nature of borders is mostly a product of memory that countered cartographic absolutism (in forms like, mental maps) and mobility that not only transformed the act of border crossing into a transgressive act, but also countered the rhetoric of 'other' through cultural hybridization and ambiguous self identification. The understanding of liquid borders in opposition to the hegemonic body of border politics further triggers the potential to go 'beyond' the borders and situate border politics not just in the context of nation-State but also globalization. Thus, this study can be furthered on the grounds of social movement in relation to borders which might potentially reveal necropolitics of governance.

Memory and mobility, therefore, can be used as an effective lens to investigate global political intersections where bodies limited and controlled by borders can potentially become bodies that are qualified to exercise agency through mobility and political consciousness.

Works Cited:

Bhabha, Homi K. *The Location of Culture*. Routledge, 1994.

Bond, Lucy and Jessica Rapson. Introduction. *The Transcultural Turn: Interrogating Memory Between and Beyond Borders*, edited by Lucy Bond and Jessica Rapson, De Gruyter, 2014, pp. 1-26. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110337617>

Butalia, Urvashi. *The other Side of Silence: Voices from the Partition of India*. Penguin Books, 1998.

Gitanjali Shree. *Tomb of Sand : A Novel*. Translated by Daisy Rockwell, HarperVia, 2023.

Ghosh, Amitav. *The Shadow Lines*. 1988. John Murray (Publishers), 2011.

Moraña, Mabel. Introduction. *Liquid Borders: Migration as Resistance*, edited by Mabel Moraña, Routledge, 2021, pp. 1-14. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003142911>

Mukherjee, Meenakshi. "Maps and Mirrors: Co-ordinates of Meaning in The Shadow Lines". *The Perishable Empire: Essays on Indian writing in English*. Oxford University Press, 2000.

---. "Narrating a Nation." *Indian Literature*, vol. 35, no. 4 (150), 1992, pp. 138–49. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/23337240. Accessed 29 July 2025.

Roy, Anjali Gera. *Memories and Postmemories of the Partition of India*. Routledge, 2020.

Rushdie, Salman. *Imaginary Homelands Essays and Criticism 1981-1991*. Penguin Books, 1991.

Sharma, Sanjay. *Multicultural Encounters*. Palgrave Macmillan London, 2006. *Springer Nature Link*, <https://doi.org/10.1057/9780230599321>.